

RELATIONSHIP AMONG TEACHER-STUDENT RATIO, SCHOOL INFRASTRUCTURE AND LEARNING OUTCOMES OF SENIOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN PHYSICS IN ADAMAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship among teacher-student ratio, school infrastructure, and learning outcomes in Physics among senior secondary school students in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Prompted by persistently low pass rates in Physics, the research adopted a correlational design, surveying a sample of 300 students across secondary schools using a validated 15-item Likert-scale questionnaire. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. Results revealed that although the teacher-student ratio was perceived as generally manageable, both school physical resources and learning resources were rated as inadequate by students. Regression analysis demonstrated a statistically significant, though weak, relationship between teacher-student ratio and learning outcomes ($R = 0.181$, $R^2 = 3.3\%$, $p < 0.05$). More robust relationships were found between school physical resources ($R = 0.640$, $R^2 = 40.9\%$, $p < 0.001$) as well as learning resources ($R = 0.550$, $R^2 = 30.2\%$, $p < 0.001$) and student performance. The findings highlight that improved infrastructure—including better laboratories, classrooms, and instructional materials—and adequate learning resources significantly enhance Physics learning outcomes, whereas teacher-student ratio, while important, plays a comparatively smaller role. The study recommends targeted investments in recruiting qualified Physics teachers and upgrading school facilities and resources to foster improved academic achievement in Physics, thereby supporting long-term scientific and technological development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Teacher-Student Ratio, Learning Outcomes, School Physical Resources, Learning Resources

INTRODUCTION

Education is vital for propelling individual as well as national development since it equips someone with the required knowledge, skills, attitudes, and even the spirit. Learning, acquiring knowledge, skills, values, and beliefs, are achieved through a process called education, which is accomplished through a systematic approach, and can be formal, non-formal, or informal. Education enhances an individual's capacity to engage with and contribute to development and active national participation (UNESCO, 2021). An education system that is well structured inspires innovation and productivity which is central to the socio-economic development of a nation. Nigeria is one of those nations which is trying to improve education with different policies that are meant to provide every citizen with the right educational opportunities. Nigeria is well aware of the opportunities education can offer, and that is why there are policies to provide universal education, but there are still

issues, especially with science which is critical for technology and economic development (Federal Ministry of Education, 2022).

Science education is the process of teaching and learning scientific ideas, principles, and methods. Its goal is to develop students' inquiry abilities, critical thinking, and comprehension of the world around them, thereby equipping them with the necessary knowledge to resolve practical problems (Nwagbo & Agbo, 2023). In addition, the education of sciences helps in the development of a nation since it is a critical factor in technological advancement and sustains the economy. It is important to note that Physics, as a fundamental part of science education, is particularly important because it is used in almost all disciplines, including engineering, medicine, and environmental science, hence, promoting the development of the society.

Physics is regarded as the science that deals with matter, energy, and the basic forces of nature. It deals with subjects such as mechanics, thermodynamics, electromagnetism, and quantum physics with the aim of explaining the universe (Halliday et al., 2020). Even with its importance, the lack of physics comprehension within the education system is striking when looking at the statistics around Nigeria and Adamawa State. More recent data has shown that the physics pass rate in WASSCE has been stagnating at under 50%, meaning students are struggling with applying physics principles and concepts (West African Examinations Council, 2023). This problem not just affects students' educational advancement; it jeopardizes the country's ability to train sufficient scientists and engineers needed for national development.

Performance in physics can be influenced by multiple factors. These may include the motivation of the student, the quality of the teacher, the involvement of the parent, and even the physical climate within the classroom. Out of all these factors, the teacher-student ratio and the school's physical infrastructure are the most important, as they have a direct bearing on the teaching and learning activities. Teacher-student ratio can be defined as the number of students who are registered to a single teacher, and this affects the degree of care and help students get in a classroom. Studies show a positive correlation between lower teacher-student ratios and effective individualized assistance, for example, in understanding higher order subjects in physics (Ogunyemi & Akinyemi, 2022). In the same way, school infrastructure encompasses all the physical structures, educational facilities, teaching materials, as well as resources necessary for learning and education, for example, the classrooms, laboratories, and libraries. School infrastructure that is sufficient and even proficient in physically teaching and practically using physics is vital. These two factors are the focus of this study on their effect on learning outcomes of the pupils of senior secondary schools in physics in Adamawa State.

Teaching and learning on any given subject in this era have become a real challenge all over the globe, teaching a subject on a one-to-one, one-to-five, one-to-30, one-to-40 or one-to-70 all have its perks and come with its challenges. Teachers in lower ratios have better and deeper persuasion with their students, enabling a better grasp on subjects which in turn enhances better and personalized feedback and holistic growth in their subjects, this is evidenced by Leigh and Ryan (2022). Rather, the style of teaching in a one-to-40 student environment has its perks too, the skill of a teacher in the said environment can make or break a student and can lead to a lower energy student or a lower motivated achiever. Looking at the teacher student ratios is very important in this instance for teaching students and teaching physics because of so many factors.

This study is needed because of the worrying physics performance among secondary school students in Adamawa State. It aims to look into the relationship between school facilities as well as the teacher-student ratio and students' educational outcomes. It is expected that the findings of the study will assist policy makers to take appropriate measures to avert the decline of physics education. It is important to note that improvement in the educational outcomes in physics is

critical not only for the immediate academic achievement of the students but also in nurturing the next generation who will propel the scientific and technological development of Nigeria.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In the context of Adamawa State in Nigeria, the performance of students in physics at the senior secondary level presents a distinctive challenge. In the ideal situation, it is expected that students will perform well and be equipped with adequate learning to pursue a degree in the sciences and/or engineering for meaningful contributions to the development of the country. Unfortunately, this is not the case as the students continue to perform poorly and the pass rates for physics in WASSCE has remained stagnant below 50% (West African Examinations Council, 2023).

There are a few underlying issues this situation can be attributed to, most of which have occurred throughout the years. They include, but are not limited to, an inadequate student-teacher ratio, limited school facilities, and a limited school infrastructure, which, both, impacts the sustainable practice of education. Studies have shown that many students, when engaged in a less-than optimal scholarly environment, lead to a decline of interest in the subject, in addition to its negative school performance (Leigh & Ryan, 2022). Moreover, an ensemble of many schools faces a profound shortage of imperative teaching tools like a lab and teaching-learning materials, which creates a lot of barriers to the teaching and learning process (Olatunji et al, 2023).

These many factors have aided in the improper teaching of courses like physics, which in turn has deepened students' inability to understand the very basic concepts. This does not only affect the scholastic aptitude of students, but it also greatly inhibits the ability to build a science and technology-based workforce, which the area greatly needs to fuel its economy. There is need to improve the state of physics education in Adamawa. To make effective changes, strategic modifications are essential. This research seeks to determine the effects of improving the school facilities and the teacher-student ratio on physics education outcomes. Addressing these factors is expected to improve students' support and resources, thereby improving their performance in physics. These changes are necessary to help build a generation of students who can drive the scientific and technological innovations needed for the growth of the country.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The study aims to investigate the relationship between teacher-student ratio, school infrastructure, learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in physics in Adamawa State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to determine:

1. The relationship between teacher-student ratio and learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics.
2. The relationship between school physical resources and learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics.
3. The relationship between school learning resources and learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions guided the study.

1. What is the level of teacher-student ratio in senior secondary school students in Adamawa State?
2. What is the level of school physical resources for senior secondary school students in Adamawa State?
3. What is the level of school learning resources for senior secondary school students in Adamawa State?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teacher-student ratio and learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between school physical resources and learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between school learning resources and learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Teacher-Student Ratio

The teacher-student ratio (also referred to as student-teacher ratio or pupil-teacher ratio) describes the comparison between the number of students and the number of teachers in a certain school, education institution, or system. It is usually described as the number of students per one teacher (for example, a ratio of 20:1 indicates that there are 20 students for each teacher). This ratio gives a very rough comparison on the possible level of per-pupil attention and is a factor which is likely to affect the instructional quality; lower ratios are associated with greater teaching flexibility, whereas higher ratios which are likely to lower the instructional quality, will mean that each teacher handles a large number of students and will affect the learning (Njoroge, Mulwa, & Kiweu, 2023; Chiu & Kuo, 2022).

School Infrastructure

School infrastructure includes the organizational frameworks and the physical features that assist the provision of education. These are such as buildings and their attending classrooms, libraries, laboratories, as well as the playgrounds, sanitation, and safety facilities, and other technology. School infrastructure should be properly established. It should promote safety, functionality, and an atmosphere conducive to learning and teaching. A school's infrastructure affects an individual's comfort, safety, resource access, and education experience. It covers the standard and the school's maintenance of the provided classrooms and their utilized features such as ramps or lifts to laboratories and other specialized rooms like computer rooms. It also includes the provision for extra-curricular and inclusive learning opportunities (Othoo, Olel, & Gogo, 2019; Earthman, 2004).

Learning Outcomes

Learning outcomes are the measurable criteria that articulate what a learner is expected to know and be able to demonstrate as a result of participating in a given course, program, or an educational activity. Learning outcomes often consist of content knowledge, practical skills, an intellectual capability, and even an aspect of attitude shift. Learning outcomes describe the intended cognitive, behavioural, or affective formal educational accomplishments, which is essentially, the goals of teaching and learning. Effective learning outcomes guide curriculum design, assist in aligning assessment tools, and help clarify educational aims and ensure they are centred on the learner. They may include the demonstration of academic mastery, critical thinking, effective and creative communication, and professional or personal development (Biggs & Tang, 2011; Ogunyemi & Adedoyin, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a correlational design. The population of the study consists of 30, 000 students offering Physics in senior secondary schools in Adamawa state. A sample of 300 students were selected using a simple random sampling technique. The data was collected using a structured questionnaire consisting of 15 items based on Likert scale response options of Strongly agree to strongly disagree. The questionnaire was validated by experts and the reliability of the questionnaire was found to be 0.76 using Cronbach Alpha method. The data collected were analyzed using SPSS version 23. Mean and standard deviation were using in answering the research questions while regression analysis was used in testing the null hypotheses.

RESULTS

The three research questions raised were answered using mean and standard deviation while the null hypotheses were tested using regression analysis.

What is the level of teacher-student ratio in senior secondary school students in Adamawa state?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on Level of Teacher-student Ratio in Senior Secondary School Students in Adamawa State

S/N	Statement	Mean	S. D	Remark
1	The number of students in the physics class is manageable.	3.93	0.97	A
2	I receive adequate individual attention from my physics teacher.	3.69	0.78	A
3	The teacher-student ratio affects my learning experience.	3.85	1.00	A
4	There are too many students in our physics class.	3.69	0.99	A
5	My teacher is able to provide personalized support in class.	3.54	0.98	A
Grand Mean		3.74	0.94	A

Students perceive the teacher-student ratio in senior secondary school physics classes as adequate, with a grand mean of 3.74 and a standard deviation of 0.94 as seen in Table 1. Although classes may be large, students report receiving sufficient individual attention and support from their teachers, suggesting the ratio is manageable and supports learning.

What is the level of school physical resources for senior secondary school students in Adamawa state?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on Level of School Physical Resources in Senior Secondary School Students in Adamawa State

S/N	Statement	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	The classrooms are adequately equipped for learning physics.	3.63	0.90	A
2	The school has sufficient laboratory facilities for practical physics.	3.48	1.03	D
3	The condition of the school buildings is conducive to learning.	3.16	1.11	D
4	I have access to essential learning materials in my physics class.	3.50	1.21	A
5	The overall physical environment of the school supports my studies.	3.29	1.10	D

Grand Mean	3.41	1.07	D
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The availability and adequacy of school physical resources are generally considered insufficient, with a grand mean of 3.41 and a standard deviation of 1.07 as shown in Table 2. While some classroom resources are adequate, laboratory facilities, building conditions, and the overall learning environment are perceived as inadequate, indicating a need for infrastructure improvement.

What is the level of school learning resources for senior secondary school students in Adamawa state?

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Responses on Level of School Learning Resources in Senior Secondary School Students in Adamawa State

S/N	Statement	Mean	S.D	Remark
1	There are sufficient textbooks available for physics students.	3.29	1.01	D
2	I have access to computers and internet facilities for my studies.	3.38	1.07	D
3	The school library has adequate resources for physics research.	3.41	1.04	D
4	I can participate in hands-on experiments due to available resources.	3.67	1.04	A
5	The learning facilities at my school enhance my understanding of physics.	3.66	1.12	A
Grand Mean		3.48	1.06	D

The results of analysis in Table 4 reveals that school learning resources are rated as inadequate, with a grand mean of 3.48 and a standard deviation of 1.06. Though students benefit from hands-on experiments and some effective learning facilities, limited access to textbooks, internet, and library materials hinders comprehensive learning in physics.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teacher-student ratio and learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics.

Table 4: Summary of Regression Analysis Results of Relationship between Teacher-student Ratio and Learning Outcomes of Senior Secondary School Students in Physics

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	R	R Square	Sig.
1	Regression	417.724	1	417.724	10.078	.181 ^a	.033	.002 ^b
	Residual	12351.513	298	41.448				
	Total	12769.237	299					

- a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), Teacher-student ratio

In Table 4, the results from the regression analysis on the relationship between teacher-student ratio and senior secondary students' learning outcomes in Physics are displayed. The analysis indicates a significant relationship, as the p-value (Sig.) is 0.002, which is below the 0.05 cutoff. Thus, the null hypothesis (H₀₁) which claims there is no relationship, is disproven. The explanatory power of the model is quite low (R Square = 0.033), showing that the teacher-student ratio only explains about 3.3% of the variance in students' Physics performance. Even though the relationship is significant, the degree

of association is rather weak ($R = 0.181$), indicating that the teacher-student ratio is not the only contributing factor for learners' performance.

H02: There is no significant relationship between school physical resources and learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics.

Table 5: Summary of Regression Analysis Results of Relationship between School Physical Resources and Learning Outcomes of Senior Secondary School Students in Physics

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	R	R Square	Sig.
1	Regression	5227.182	1	5227.182	.640 ^a	.409		.000 ^b
	Residual	7542.054	298	25.309				
	Total	12769.237	299					

- a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), School Physical Facilities

Table 5 demonstrates the result of the regression analysis on the relationship between physical resources of the school and the learning outcomes of Physics. The analysis result in the table gives p value as 0.000. This is significantly less than 0.05 and hence the null hypothesis (H02) is rejected. R Square value of 0.409 indicates that physical resources of the school account for approximately 40.9% of the students' academic performance variation. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.640$) offers further confirmation for the analysis results. It also denotes a moderate to strong association that physical infrastructure and enhance the facilities and learning environment will improve the academic performance of students in Physics.

H03: There is no significant relationship between school learning resources and learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics.

Table 6: Summary of Regression Analysis Results of Relationship between School Learning Resources and Learning Outcomes of Senior Secondary School Students in Physics

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	R	R Square	Sig.
1	Regression	3856.754	1	3856.754	.550 ^a	.302		.000 ^b
	Residual	8912.482	298	29.908				
	Total	12769.237	299					

- a. Dependent Variable: Academic Performance
- b. Predictors: (Constant), School Learning Resources

Table 6 evaluates how the availability of school learning resources affects students' academic performance in Physics. The outcome indicates a significant correlation with a p-value of 0.000, resulting in the rejection of the null hypothesis (H03). The R Square value was 0.302 which indicates that 30.2% of the change in academic performance is

attributed to learning resources. The correlation coefficient ($R = 0.550$) suggests a moderate positive relationship, meaning that students' performance in Physics is considerably impacted by the availability of textbooks, libraries, digital learning tools, and other relevant materials.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study reveal a significant relationship between the teacher-student ratio and the learning outcomes of senior secondary school students in Physics. A favourable teacher-student ratio is vital for creating an environment conducive to effective teaching and learning. A better (lower) teacher-student ratio improves the outcomes of learning which is a prerequisite for favourable performance. This is supported by Chiu and Kuo (2022), who concluded that a lower teacher-student ratio is associated with increased achievement and engagement of students, especially for within Physics and other advanced courses that require significant attention. Their research underscored the crucial role of tailored teaching in achieving mastery of complex scientific principles. In the same way, Olanrewaju and Zubairu (2023) noted that students from lower teacher-student ratio schools performed better in science. Their explanation included more engaging lessons, more direct supervision from the teacher, better feedback and other teaching and learning enabling processes. The current finding differs from the study by Njoroge, Mulwa, and Kiweu (2023), who reported no significant relationship concerning the teacher-student ratio in academic achievement ($p = .597$). This difference could be contextual in terms of the educational setting, the teaching staff, or the presence of additional learning materials that could buffer the impact of class size on performance.

The study establishes a significant relationship between school physical resources and learning outcomes in Physics among senior secondary school students. It highlights that facilities such as well-equipped laboratories, well-ventilated classrooms, and adequate instructional materials significantly enhance student engagement, participation, and comprehension in Physics. This finding aligns with that of Adeyemo and Osunade (2021), who emphasized that the adequacy of physical infrastructure improves the teaching and learning of science subjects by promoting hands-on activities and active learning. In a similar vein, Adewale and Adewale (2022) found that the condition of physical school facilities directly influences students' performance, especially in science-based subjects that require practical engagement. Likewise, Uche and Olibie (2019) noted that a lack of physical resources in Nigerian secondary schools is a major barrier to effective teaching and learning, particularly in Physics and Chemistry. These studies collectively affirm that investment in school infrastructure is a key driver of academic success in science education.

The study reveals that there is a relationship that is significant between the educational resources available in the school and the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Physics. This is in agreement with Ogunyemi and Adedoyin (2023) who stressed that students' provisions of learning resources such as textbooks, visual aids, and even electronic learning tools significantly enhanced their academic performance. This is in agreement with Okonkwo (2015) who noted that proper application of instructional materials improves students' performance in the three domains of psychosocial learning (cognitive, affective, and psychomotor) and thus makes the teaching of Physics much more interesting and understandable.

As every bit of evidence found thus far corroborates the earlier conclusion, there is a direct link where accessing lessons and resources available positively influences the student's performance through the use of the instructional materials. Othoo, Olel and Gogo (2019) adduced this as a strong correlation with the way a student's performance is affected in a science area even hypothetically, if a proper provision and use of lesson resources was available. From these studies, there is a strong correlation between the appropriate use and an adequate provision of instructional resources that could dramatically sharpen

a student's abstract scientific thinking and sharpen their academic outcome. The convergence and corroboration of the studies give and strengthen the argument that provision of materials and their proper utilization foster deeper understanding in learning Physics.

CONCLUSION

It is therefore concluded that improving teacher-student ratios, enhancing school physical infrastructure, and providing adequate educational resources are essential strategies for promoting better learning outcomes in Physics among senior secondary school students.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made.

1. Government and school administrators should recruit more qualified Physics teachers to reduce class sizes and ensure more effective teaching and individual student support.
2. Schools should be adequately equipped with functional laboratories, well-ventilated classrooms, and necessary Physics apparatus to create an environment conducive to practical and theoretical learning.
3. Educational stakeholders should ensure the consistent supply of up-to-date textbooks, instructional materials, and digital learning tools to support effective teaching and learning of Physics.

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